

Graduate Employability: New Graduates Perceptions of important, urgency and performance of Employability Skills in Malaysia

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Erni Tanius* ⁽²⁾Husna bt Johari ⁽³⁾Astri Yulia ⁽⁴⁾Chin Siong Heng ⁽⁵⁾Khairul Hanim Pazim

⁽¹⁾Faculty of Business and Accounting, Universiti Selangor, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia ⁽²⁾Collage of Business, University Utara Malaysia, Kedah, Malaysia ⁽³⁾Faculty Education and Social Science, University Selangor, Berjuntai Bestari, Selangor, Malaysia ⁽⁴⁾Faculty of Cognitive ⁽⁴⁾Sciences and Human Development, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (UNIMAS) Sarawak, Malaysia ⁽⁵⁾School of Business & Economics, University Malaysia Sabah, Sabah, Malaysia (* Corresponding Author)

Abstract

Graduate employability becomes a severe issue globally; industry, university, and government blame each other for the matter getting worse. This study focus on new graduates opinion of important, urgency and their performance on employability skills required by the employer in order to be employed by industry. 1656 new graduates from Peninsular Malaysia, Sabah, and Sarawak participated in this study. The questionnaire used to gather the information, meanwhile the employability skills variables, emphasis on four types of skill; they are basic skills, applied, interpersonal and 21st-century skills. The data analyzed by using SPSS and descriptive statistics, correlation, as well multiple regressions use to answer the research question. The finding indicated that new graduates believed that the 21st-century skills were the most important factor to predict employment opportunity while the basic skills were the least important. The correlation results suggest that the perceived importance of the aspects highly related with urgency. The result also found that interpersonal skills negatively linked with employment opportunity. Finally, the study suggested that industry and university need to collaborate on identifying and developing employability skills among new graduates.

Keywords: *graduate employability, perception, important, urgency, performance, employability skills, Malaysia*

INTRODUCTION

The employability issue among Malaysian new graduates categorized as a critical issue by the Ministry of Education (2015). Current literature indicates that the reasons are the mismatch between employers' expectations and the graduates' employability skills or is known as skill gaps. Malaysia, like other countries, experiences a serious skill gap: The current graduates' skill supply is not able to meet the skill demanded by industry. The increase in the number of graduates seems unable to close the gaps.

Literature listed the key essential in increasing the employment opportunity among new graduates, such as Clarke M (2017) suggested that the dimensions of human capital, social capital, individual attributes, individual behaviors, perceived employability and labor market factors. Meanwhile, Denise Jackson & Nicholas Wilton (2017) argued that the pre-professional identity (PPI) formation contributes to employment opportunity. It relates to an understanding of and connection with the skills, qualities, conduct, culture, and ideology of a student's intended profession and it can be developed during university years.

The research was done by Harry T, Chinyamurindi, WT, & Mjoli. T. (2018) indicated that there are five factors contributed to employability: (1) poor socio-economic status, (2) an education system, (3) curriculum issues, (4) the choice of higher education institution and (5) social connections to which the student belongs to. Nevertheless, Erni Tanius (2018) study on 299 organizations, 607 managers, and 700 new graduates found out that students claimed that applied skills (Problem-solving skills and multi-tasking); interpersonal skills (able to adapt to different environment and able to lead a group) and 21st century skills (working under challenging deadline or an urgent job and research skill) skills that required by industry. Finally Sílvia Monteiro, Joaquim

Armando Ferreira, Leandro S. Almeida. (2018), suggested that graduates students should equip with career management resources to ensure the smooth transition from university to the labor market.

Hence this study would like to answer the following questions; 1. What are the new graduates' perceptions of importance, urgency, and their performance of employability skills? 2. What factors influence their perception? 3. Do graduate perceptions of importance, urgency, and their performance contribute to their employment opportunity?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Skills gap exists across nations and industries, Business news (2015) reported that The World Bank expects Malaysia employment will rise to 12.7 million by 2020, from 10.4 million in 2010 and 11.3 million in 2014 and some of these new jobs will be in economically crucial to industry and have identified as the key drivers of growth and development of economy.

Literature indicated that employer and graduates are having the opposite opinion on the skills gap. The employer claimed Malaysian graduates are far from ideal, and they added that graduates from private education are better than those from public universities (Kee-Cheok Cheong, Christopher Hill, & Yin-Ching Leong 2016). However it differed with the finding on Ariel M. Plantilla (2017), and Mehrotra A (2017) studied indicated that employers were very much satisfied on the performance of graduates regarding knowledge and understanding of the job, general skills, specialized skills and personal qualities demonstrated in the workplace. However, graduates said that are ready to enter the workplace (Erni and Suhana . 2015).

The skill gap is not only hit new graduates but the industry as well. Grant Thornton (2013) found that 62% of firms in Malaysia have difficulty in finding workers with the right skills, while 48% identify the lack of talent as a constraint for future growth. Meanwhile in E& E sectors experience the similar (Business Consulting, 2012). CareerBuilder (2013) studied on 1,025 employers, 205 academics and 1,524 job seekers, found out that more than half of surveyed employers reported they have open jobs for which they cannot find qualified candidates.

Deloitte and The Manufacturing Institute (2014) reported that even in high unemployment rate above 9% in the US, the employer still having problems to fill positions, 5% of their jobs remain unfilled simply because of they unable to find the right people with the right skills. Ministry of Human Resources (2015) reported that out of 11,527 vacancies, only 3,457 or 30% filled up by the total 32,331 registered graduate job seekers.

This scenario is worse in West Malaysia (about 71% unfilled vacancies) than in East Malaysia (about 30% unfilled vacancies). Zaliza Hanapi & Mohd Safarin Nordin (2013) revealed that job vacancies are critically increasing each year. Finally, the investigation by Erni (2015), Erni and Che Manisah (2012) found out that the industries complained that graduates lack technical/applied skills during the internship.

The impact of the skills gap is huge as reported by Wormer K, Finkelstein S, and Shuang Han (2014) and Giff G. et al. (2015), it gives impact to company ability in implementing new technologies while achieving productivity targets. This issue continues to widen and affect many aspects of industries and economy of the country. In a long-term, this issue threatened the nation's ability to compete in the fast-moving global economy and hampered the target of achieving vision 2050 to become a high-income nation.

Works of literature list out the central critical skills gap are in applied/technical skills, interpersonal skill, and 21st-century skills. They are mainly on critical/analytical thinking, oral communication, active listening, prioritization and focus, as well as time management, problem-solving, collaboration, creativity, and innovation skills. Besides, 21st-century skills; industry looking employees have the ability in information technology application, teamwork/collaboration, diversity, self-management, professional Relationships, professional Appearance, Negotiation, soft skills area, enthusiasm, and flexibility abilities — additionally, the leadership, ethics & professionalism, and self-management skills. (Bellanca J. and Brandt R, 2010; Susie Quern Pratt&

Jenny Ellis Richards, 2014; Salina, D., Nurazariah, A., Noraina Mazuin, S., & Jegatheesan, R. (2011); Mohamad Shukri Abdul Hamid, Rafikul Islam and Noor Hazilah Abd Manaf, 2014; Mohamad Idham Md Razak, Asliza Mohd Yusof, Wan Nor Syazana, Wan Effa Jaafar & Adi Hakim Talib. (2014); Verica Babić & Marko Slavković, 2011, Yasmin Mohd Adnan, Md Nasir Daud, Anuar Alias & Muhammad Najib Razali, 2012; Kelebogile Paadi. (2014); Hazril Azmin Saari & Abdullah Mat Rashid, 2013; and Lowden et al., 2011).

METHODOLOGY

The target population of this was 700 new graduates from Malaysia (Peninsular Malaysia, Sabah, and Sarawak). Projection to Latent Structures (PLS) used to analyze the data. Data Analyses in this study will conduct in four phases. First, preliminary analyses, i.e., descriptive statistics, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Pearson correlation will be conducted to provide baseline statistics and to examine if the data meet the assumptions of PLS to establish baseline model.

FINDING

1. Student Demographic Profile

Table1. Demographic Profile of Student Respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
N total		1656	
Gender	Male	475	28.7
	Female	1181	71.3
Age	20 or younger	210	12.7
	21-25	1359	82.1
	26 and older	87	5.3
Race	Malay	1019	61.5
	Chinese	120	7.2
	Indian	247	14.9
	Others	270	16.3
Nationality	Malaysian	1637	98.9
	Non-Malaysian	19	1.1

From the 1656 students participated in the research, 28.7% of the students were males while the other 71.3% were female students. This nature where there are more female than male students reflects the population in which the data collected from students of the business and management field dominated by female students. A vast majority of the student participants were aged between 21-25 (1359 students) and were Malays (1019) with only 19 international students.

2. Descriptive Statistics for Students’ Ratings of the Measured Skills

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Student Variables

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
BS_Importance	1656	1.90	5.00	4.2491	.55745
BS_Urgency	1656	1.60	9.50	4.0879	.61405
BS_Performance	1656	1.60	5.00	4.1008	.54489
AS_Importance	1656	2.00	5.00	4.1434	.62391
AS_Urgency	1656	2.10	8.20	4.0568	.58419
AS_Performance	1656	1.40	5.00	4.0160	.58359
IS_Importance	1656	2.00	5.00	4.2626	.56894
IS_Urgency	1656	1.82	5.00	4.1615	.64576
IS_Performance	1656	1.18	5.00	4.1501	.57257
CS_Importance	1656	2.20	9.90	4.3291	.51504
CS_Urgency	1656	1.80	5.00	4.2013	.58854
CS_Performance	1656	1.70	5.00	4.0832	.58905
EPO	1656	1.00	5.00	3.2696	.96493
Valid N (listwise)	1656				

There were 1656 students participated from various universities and colleges in Malaysia. The mean values in the above table show that students, on average, rated the skills higher when asking on the importance as compared to questions about the urgency of the skills needed for employment and their performance on the skills.

Correlation Analysis

Table 3. Basic Skill Correlations

Correlations		BS_Importance	BS_Urgency	BS_Performance
BS_Importance	Pearson Correlation	1	.563**	.488**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
BS_Urgency	Pearson Correlation	.563**	1	.553**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
BS_Performance	Pearson Correlation	.488**	.553**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	1656	1656	1656

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above presents the correlations between the ratings of the Basic Skills: importance, urgency, and performance. The Pearson's correlation values show that the rating of importance significantly correlated with urgency ($r = .563, p < .01$). This result indicates that students rated the skills as important for employment when at the same time they think the skills are also urgently needed. The statistically significant correlations were also documented between students' rating of basic skills urgency and performance ($r = .553, p < .01$), and importance and performance ($r = .488, p < .01$). These values, however, are smaller than the relationship between importance and urgency.

Table 4. Applied Skill Correlation

		AS_Importance	AS_Urgency	AS_Performance
AS_Importance	Pearson Correlation	1	.626**	.503**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
AS_Urgency	Pearson Correlation	.626**	1	.585**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
AS_Performance	Pearson Correlation	.503**	.585**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	1656	1656	1656

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows the correlation results among the applied skill ratings: importance, urgency, and performance. Importance and urgency were statistically significantly, highly correlated ($r = .626, p < .01$) which indicates that when students rated the applied skills as important, they were also highly like to rate them as urgently needed for employment. The correlations between importance and performance was the weakest ($r = .503, p < .01$), and urgency and performance was moderate ($r = .585, p < .01$).

Table 5. Interpersonal Skill Correlations

		IS_Importance	IS_Urgency	IS_Performance
IS_Importance	Pearson Correlation	1	.660**	.575**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
IS_Urgency	Pearson Correlation	.660**	1	.591**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
IS_Performance	Pearson Correlation	.575**	.591**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	1656	1656	1656

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results of correlation analysis on interpersonal skill variables similarly show the same pattern in which importance highly related to urgency ($r = .660, p < .01$). This finding indicates that the more the students think that the skill is important, the more urgent the skill needed for employment. The other two correlations were lesser in Pearson's r values (for urgency and performance, $r = .591, p < .01$; and for importance and performance, $r = .575, p < .01$).

Table 6. The 21st Century Skill Correlations

		CS_Importance	CS_Urgency	CS_Performance
CS_Importance	Pearson Correlation	1	.667**	.536**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
CS_Urgency	Pearson Correlation	.667**	1	.576**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	1656	1656	1656
CS_Performance	Pearson Correlation	.536**	.576**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	1656	1656	1656

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Above table presents the results of the correlation analysis among the 21st-century skill ratings (i.e., importance, urgency, and performance). For the relationship between importance and urgency, the correlation was statistically significant, highly correlated ($r = .667, p < .01$) which indicates that when students rated the 21st-century skills as important, they were also highly like to rate them as urgently needed for employment. The correlations between importance and performance was the lowest ($r = .536, p < .01$), and urgency and performance was moderate ($r = .576, p < .01$).

3. Predicting Employment Opportunity

To investigate the influence of the four measured skills (i.e., basic skills, applied skills, interpersonal skills, and the 21st-century skills), we examined the role of the students' ratings on importance, urgency, and performance in predicting their employment opportunity. In order to test the effects, multiple regression analysis performed. First, we looked at the influence of the importance of the skills on employment opportunity. The result showed that the important aspects explained 11.5% variance in employment opportunity. The variance explained accounted by the predictor variables was not large, but considering the research is about behavior, 10% of the variance is enough to seek an explanation of what factors account for the effects.

Table 7. Multiple Regression Table for Importance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	4.132	.205		20.117	.000
	BS_Importance	-.337	.055	-.195	-6.170	.000
	AS_Importance	.442	.059	.286	7.491	.000
	IS_Importance	-.857	.078	-.505	-10.996	.000
	CS_Importance	.552	.063	.295	8.797	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EPO

The table above shows that all skills were statistically significant ($p < .05$) in predicting employment opportunity. The most important factors to predict employment opportunity ($\beta = .295$) followed by applied skills ($\beta = .286$) was 21st-century skills. Surprisingly, interpersonal skills negatively linked with employment opportunity ($\beta = -.505$) which indicates that the more the students think the interpersonal skills as important, the lower their employment opportunity.

The second aspect we analyzed was the role of students' perceived urgency of the skills on their employment opportunity. The variance accounted by the criterion variables was moderate (R Square = 13.5%). This finding shows that the students' perceived urgency of the skills can moderately predict their employment opportunity.

Table 8. Multiple Regression for Urgency

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	3.125	.178		17.548	.000
	BS_Urgency	-.246	.051	-.157	-4.821	.000
	AS_Urgency	.171	.058	.103	2.957	.003
	IS_Urgency	-.733	.062	-.491	-11.870	.000
	CS_Urgency	.836	.061	.510	13.784	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EPO

The above table presents the multiple regression results showing the influence of each criterion variable on employment opportunity. All variables significantly linked with employment opportunity ($p < .05$). The result suggested on the important effect of the urgency of the 21st-century skills on employment opportunity ($\beta = .510$) followed by applied skills ($\beta = .103$). The urgency of interpersonal skills was also negatively linked with employment opportunity ($\beta = -.491$). The effect of basic skills ($\beta = -.153$) and applied skills ($\beta = .103$) urgency were statistically significant but small effects.

The third factor evaluated was the students' self-reported performance on the measured skills and how these skills predict their employment opportunity. The variance explained accounted by the predictor variables were fairly small (R square = 5.8%, $R = .241$, $F = 25.467$, $p < .01$). The small effect of performance on employment opportunity could be due to the self-report nature of the survey. When students asked about their performance, some of the answers could be biased, hence, the lower influence. However, F test still indicates the statistically significant result.

Table 8. Multiple Regression for Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	3.332	.190		17.496	.000
	BS_Performance	-.079	.070	-.045	-1.130	.259
	AS_Performance	-.535	.069	-.324	-7.744	.000
	IS_Performance	-.042	.065	-.025	-.643	.520
	CS_Performance	.633	.075	.386	8.428	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EPO

The regression result presented in the table above shows that the 21st-century skill performance was the strongest predictor of employment opportunity ($\beta = .386$). The applied skill performance, however, had a negative effect on employment opportunity ($\beta = -.324$). The basic and interpersonal skill performances, on the other hand, did not have a significant effect on employment opportunity.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Across all aspects, the study among student respondents found that the 21st-century skills were the most important factor to predict employment opportunity while the basic skills were the least important. The correlation results suggest that the perceived importance of the aspects highly related with urgency. Hence, when students think that these aspects are important, they also perceive the factors to urgently needed for employment. One surprising finding was that interpersonal skills negatively linked with employment opportunity. This adverse effect suggests that interpersonal skills can interfere with employment opportunity. However, it is important to note the respondents in this study mainly is not highly experienced employees; most of them were fresh graduates and interns. Their perception of interpersonal skills may not have fully established.

From the results above, the study concluded the following model for employment opportunity from the student perspective (see the figure below). The dotted line indicates the weak influence of performance on employment opportunity. This model suggests that for fresh and prospective graduates, the most critical aspects to predict their employment opportunity are their perception that the 21st-century skills and other skills are important and urgent. This awareness among the students could lead them to see how much they need to master these skills.

Figure 1. The Student Model

REFERENCES

- i. Ariel M. Plantilla (2017), *Graduates Performance in the Workplace: Employers' Perspective*, Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Vol. 5 No.2, pg. 186-198, P-ISSN 2350-7756, www.apjmr.com
- ii. Bellanca J. and Brandt R. (2010), *21st Century Skills: Rethinking How Students Learn*, http://soltreemrls3/study_guides/21st_Century_Skills_Study_Guide.pdf
- iii. Business Consulting (2012), *E&E Sector Study on the Supply-Demand of Talent in Malaysia*, Project Kolman Final Report.
- iv. Business News (2015), *How Malaysians abroad are bridging a skills gap*, [thestar.com.my /Business/Business-News/ Friday, 24 April 2015](http://thestar.com.my/Business/Business-News/Friday,24April2015)
- v. Career Builder (2013) *The Shocking Truth About Skills Gap*
- vi. Clarke, M. (2017). *Rethinking graduate employability: The role of capital, individual attributes, and context*. *Studies in Higher Education*, 41, 1–15. doi: 10.1080/03075079.2017.1294152[Taylor & Francis Online], , [Google Scholar]
- vii. Deloitte and The Manufacturing Institute (2014) *Unwavering Commitment: The Public's View of the Manufacturing Industry Today*.
- viii. David Smith, Katherine LaVelle, Breck Marshall and Susan Cantrell (2013) *Do you have the skills to compete? Point of View October 2013, No. 1*
- ix. Denise Jackson & Nicholas Wilton (2017) *Career choice status among undergraduates and the influence of career management competencies and perceived employability*, *Journal of Education and Work*, 30:5, 552-569, DOI: [10.1080/13639080.2016.1255314](https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2016.1255314) However,
- x. Erni Tanius (2018), *Employability Skills – A Study on the Perception of Business Students Graduate and Employers in Malaysia*, *Asia Pacific Journal of Research in Business Management*, Vol. 9, Issue 1, January 2018 Impact Factor: 5.16, ISSN: (2229-4104)
 - a. www.skirec.org
- xi. Erni (2012), *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Industrial Training and the Relationship with employment Opportunity*, *Colloquium of Unisel. Research Publications*, 2-3 October 2012, pp. 29
- xii. Erni Tanius (2015), *Business' Students Industrial Training: Performance and Employment Opportunity*
- xiii. Erni Tanius and Suhana (2015), *A Study on Factors Contribute to Work Readiness of new Entrances in the Workforce*
- xiv. Giff G. et al. (2015), *the skills gap in U.S. Manufacturing 2015 and beyond*, *Manufacturing Institute*.
- xv. Grant Thornton (2013), <http://www.grantthornton.com.my> 12. Harris Interactive (2013) *Bridge That Gap: Analyzing the Student Skill Index*, www.chegg.com/pulse.
- xvi. Hazril Azmin Saari & Abdullah Mat Rashid. (2013). *Competency Level of Employability Skills among the Apprentices of the National Dual Training System: A Comparative Analysis of Industry Perception*. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2-12.
- xvii. Kelebogile Paadi. (2014). *Perceptions On Employability Skills Necessary To Enhance Human Resource Management Graduates Prospects of Securing A Relevant Place In The Labour Market*. *European Scientific Journal*, 132-143.
- xviii. Lowden et al., 2011, *Employers Perception of the Employability Skills of New Graduates*, the SCRE Centre Research in Education, University of Glasgow, http://www.edge.co.uk/media/63412/employability_skills.
- xix. Mehrotra A (2017), *Employers' Feedback on Business Graduates*, *US-China Education Review A*, April 2017, Vol. 7, No. 4, 190-199doi: 10.17265/2161-623X/2017.4.002
- xx. Ministry of Education (2015), [www.hhttp// mohe.gov.my](http://www.mohe.gov.my)
- xxi. Mohamad Idham Md Razak, Asliza Mohd Yusof, Wan Nor Syazana, Wan Effa Jaafar & Adi Hakim Talib. (2014), *Factors Influencing Unemployment among Graduates in Malaysia*. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 172-173.

- xxii. *Mohamad Shukri Abdul Hamid, Rafikul Islam, and Noor Hazilah Abd Manaf (2014) Employability Skills Development Approach: An application of the Analytic Network Process, Asian Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 19, No. 1, 93–111, 2014.*
- xxiii. *Sílvia Monteiro, Joaquim Armando Ferreira, Leandro S. Almeida. (2018) Self-perceived competency and self-perceived employability in higher education: the mediating role of career adaptability. Journal of Further and Higher Education 0:0, pages 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2018.1542669>*
- xxiv. *Salina, D., Nurazariah, A., Noraina Mazuin, S., & Jegatheesan, R. (2011). Enhancing university business curriculum using importance-performance approach: A case study of Business Management Faculty of a university in Malaysia. International Journal of Educational Management, 25(6), 1–21.*
- xxv. *Susie Quern Pratt & Jenny Ellis Richards (2014) Soft Skill Development in Youth Employment: A Scan of the Landscape, <http://www.dupontfund.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Soft-Skill-Development2.pdf>*
- xxvi. *Verica Babić & Marko Slavković. (2011). Soft And Hard Skills Development: A Current Situation in Serbian Companies. (pp. 408-414). Serbia: International Conference.*
- xxvii. *Wormer K, Finkelstein S, and Shuang Han (2014) Skills Gaps: The Ills-Prepared Workforce, www.umsl.edu/business/skills-set.pdf*
- xxviii. *Yasmin Mohd Adnan, Md Nasir Daud, Anuar Alias & Muhammad Najib Razali. (2012). Importance of Soft Skills for Graduates in the Real Estate Programmes in Malaysia. Journal of Surveying, Construction & Property, 2-13.*
- xxix. *Zaliza Hanapi & Mohd Safarin Nordin (2013), Unemployment Among Malaysia Graduates: Graduates’ Attributes, Lecturers’ Competency, and Quality of Education, International Conference on Education & Educational Psychology 2013 (ICEEPSY 2013), Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 112 (2014) 1056 – 1063.*